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NEUROBLASTOMA AND ITS THERAPY - A REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

Neuroblastoma (NBL) is a malignancy of the sympathetic nervous system seen in children, infants, foetus, and embryos. The organs likely to affect include Adrenal glands, above the kidneys or nervous tissue adjacent to spine, neck, chest and pelvis. Skin, Bone, Lymph nodes, Bone marrow are effected by metastasis. The most common symptoms seen are a lump in the abdomen, chest or neck, Bulging eyes, Dark circles around the eyes, Bone pain, Swollen stomach & troubled breathing in babies, Painless, bluish lumps under the skin in babies and inability to move a body part. Inability to empty the bladder, Loss of movement of the hips, legs, or feet, uncontrolled eye movements or leg and feet movements. Disease can be diagnosed by Complete Blood Count, Biopsy, and Genetic studies, CT- Scan, PET CT-Scan and MRI. Treatment can be done by surgery, radiation therapy, chemotherapy, biologic therapy, or a combination. Anti-GD2 monoclonal antibody (mAb) in combination with systemic cytokine immunotherapy shows clinical efficacy in high-risk NBL patients. Targeted therapy using Histone Deacetylase Inhibitors (HDACi) is currently being explored in cancer treatment.

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INTRODUCTION

The type of cancer that starts in very early forms of nerve cells (called neuroblasts) found in an embryo or fetus, in children is called neuroblastoma¹⁰. The term neuro means nerves, while blastoma refers to cancer¹. Adrenal glands present above the kidney are effected and other effectable organs include nervous tissue that runs along the spine, neck, chest and pelvis. It spreads to other organs such as the bone marrow, bone, lymph nodes, liver and skin². Diagnosis can be done by complete blood count, Biopsy, Genetic studies, Aspiration, CT scan, MRI. Treatment strategies include surgery, radiation therapy, chemotherapy, biologic therapy, or a combination³.

CAUSES:-

The causes and aetiology of tumor is unknown. Almost half of the tumors are seen at birth. Major role is played by genes & occurs in many areas of the body. Tumors are mostly developed in tissues that form sympathetic nervous system that controls pulse, blood pressure, hormonal balance. Most of the tumors are believed to be present in the abdomen, adrenal gland, bones, spine, arms and legs and is spreadable to bone marrow, liver, lymph, skin, around eyes^[4].

SYMPTOMS:-

Hormones were released by tumors that troubles tissues and organs in other parts of the body which are addressed as paraneoplastic syndromes. The symptoms include:

- Constant diarrhea, fever, sweating, rapid heartbeat;
- High blood pressure (causing irritability);
- Reddening (flushing) of the skin¹.

The uncommon set of symptoms is called the opsoclonus-myooclonus-ataxia syndrome or “dancing eyes, dancing feet.” Children effected often present rapid eye movements (opsoclonus), twitch-like muscle spasms (myoclonus), and uncoordination while standing or walking is seen (ataxia)¹.

The Primary symptoms usually include fever, feeling sick & pain, loss of appetite, weight loss, and diarrhea. Other symptoms depends on the site of the tumor and includes:-

- Bone pain or tenderness (if the cancer spreads to bones)
- Increased heartbeat (tachycardia), flushed& red skin, profuse sweating
- Difficulty breathing and chronic cough is seen if the cancer has spread to the chest
- Enlarged abdomen due to excess fluid
- Pale skin & bluish color around the eyes⁴.

Symptoms of Brain and nervous system seems to be:-

- Inability to empty the bladder
- Paralysis of legs, hip and feet
- Uncontrolled eye movements

PATHOPHYSIOLOGY:-**Chromosomal and molecular markers-**

- ◆ MYCN is an oncogene that is found to be over expressed in patients with neuroblastoma and have been used to evaluate the progress and risk assessment in patients^[5]. Amplification of distal arm of second chromosome of MYCN is seen.
- ◆ The lower stages of the disease are correlated with the expression of H-ras oncogene.
- ◆ The most common chromosomal abnormality seen is the deletion of short arm of chromosome¹.
- ◆ The advanced stage of disease is more common with deletion of 1p near diploid tumors & most of the deletions are seen at the 1p36 area of the chromosome^[5].
- ◆ TrkA, TrkB TrkC are three neurotrophin gene products that code for nerve growth factors and amplification of MYCN gene is intercorrelated with the expression of TrkA and correlates with good prognosis in patients who are in stage 1,2 and 4s^[5].
- ◆ Interruption of normal apoptosis is also a cause for neuroblastoma.
- ◆ Increased levels of RNA telomerase, poor expression of glucoprotein CD44 on tumor cell indicates poor prognosis & confers a multi-drug resistant phenotype in some cancers.

DIAGNOSIS:-

According to international criteria developed by an International Neuroblastoma Risk Group task force, a diagnosis of neuroblastoma can be made if:

- Bone marrow is tested for neuroblastoma cells and higher than normal levels of catecholamines in urine are detected in more than 85% of patients.
- Biopsy is done which is nothing but removal of a small amount of tissue to examine under the microscope¹⁷.
 - ▲ Blood and urine samples are collected and tested for blood cell count, clotting tests¹⁷.
 - ▲ Renal and hepatic function tests.
 - ▲ Change in the oncogene MYCN, which is responsible for cell growth is studied in case of family history.
 - ▲ Genetic tests to determine germ line mutations in PHOX2B or ALK are done¹².
 - ▲ Bone marrow has both solid and liquid parts. Removing of fluid sample with a needle and studying the sample is called as Bone marrow Aspiration.
 - ▲ Removal of solid part of bone marrow is also done which is called Bone marrow Biopsy³.
 - ▲ Computed tomography (CT or CAT) scan: - A CT scan creates a 3-dimensional picture of the inside of the body using x-rays taken from different angles. A computer then combines these images into a detailed, cross-sectional view that shows any abnormalities or tumors. A CT scan can also be used to measure the tumor's size. A special dye called a contrast medium is usually given before the scan to provide better detail on the image. This dye is injected into a patient's vein^{3, 17}.
 - ▲ Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI):- An MRI uses magnetic fields, not x-rays, to produce detailed images of the brain and spinal column. MRI can also be used to measure the tumor's size. A special dye called a contrast medium is given before the scan to create a clearer picture. This dye is injected into a patient's vein. An MRI is better at showing tumors around the spine, and it is essential to look at a tumor that is near where nerves leave the spinal column, which can press on the spinal cord³.
 - ▲ Meta-iodobenzylguanidine is the protein absorbed by neuroblastoma cells. Linkage of this protein to small amount of radioactive iodine is used to find neuroblastoma in bones, bone marrow and other parts of body³.
 - ▲ Positron emission tomography is usually combined with chromo tomography which is used to create pictures of organs and tumors. This is generally used for patients where MIBG is failed to detect the tumors³.
 - ▲ Echos are made using high energy sound waves (ULTRA SOUND) and pictures are developed (SONOGRAM) which are used to look for tumors¹⁷.

STAGES OF NEUROBLASTOMA: - 4 stages of neuroblastoma.

- ★ In stage 1, tumors are present in only one area and can be completely removed by surgery.
- ★ Stage 2 is divided into 2A & 2B
 - In Stage 1, the tumor is in only one area and all of the tumor that can be seen is completely removed during surgery³.
 - In Stage 2 is divided into stages 2A and 2B.
 - Stage 2A: Tumor is present only in one area and cannot be completely removed by surgery.
 - Stage 2B: It is same as the stage 2 but the tumor cells are found in lymph nodes¹³.
- ★ Stage 3, the tumor cannot be removed completely during surgery and spreads to other sides of lymph nodes and tissues.
- ★ Stage 4 is again categorized into stages 4 and 4S.
 - In Stage 4: the tumor has spread to distant lymph nodes or other parts of the body.
 - In stage 4S: For the child younger than 12 months, the cancer spreads to the skin, liver, and/or bone marrow³.

GENERAL TREATMENT: -

Treatment for neuroblastoma needs a multidisciplinary approach involving a surgeon, chemotherapist and radiotherapist and the treatments include:

- Surgery
- Radiation therapy - MIBG radiotherapy.
- Chemotherapy- Cyclophosphamide, Dinutuximab, Doxorubicin Hydrochloride, Vincristine sulfate, Topotecan, Irinotecan, Temozolomide, Cisplatin and Etoposide.
- Immunotherapy- Interleukins (Aldesleukin), Granulocyte growth factors (Sargramostim), Monoclonal antibodies (Dinutuximab).
- Targeted therapy- Bortezomib, Crizotinib, Vorinostat, Lenalidomide, Temsirolimus, Sorafenib, Nifurtimox, and Lestaurtinib.
- Hormone therapy- estrogens, progesterone and testosterone.
- Stem cell transplant- Tandem transplant, allogeneic stem cell transplant.
- Precision medicine ^[8, 19]

Treatment of low-risk neuroblastoma involves:

- Surgery followed by observation and based on size of tumor.
- Chemotherapy with or without surgery, for children with symptoms, children whose tumor has continued to grow and cannot be removed by surgery, or children with unfavorable tumor biology.
- Observation for infants younger than 6 months who have small adrenal tumors.
- Radiation therapy can be used in tumors causing serious side effects and patients showing delayed response.
- A clinical trial of treatment based on the tumor's response to treatment and tumor biology ^[6, 15].

Treatment of intermediate-risk neuroblastoma includes:

- Chemotherapy for children with symptoms & to shrink a tumor that cannot be removed by surgery.
- Surgery alone for infants done before or after chemotherapy
- Observation for certain children.
- Radiation therapy to treat tumors that are causing serious problems and do not respond effectively to chemotherapy or surgery.
- A clinical trial of treatment based on the tumor's response to treatment and tumor biology ^[6, 15, 18].

Treatment of high-risk neuroblastoma is done by:

A combination of chemotherapy, surgery, stem cell rescue, radiation therapy & Monoclonal antibody with granulocyte-macrophage colony stimulating factor and isotretinoin.

There is no standard treatment for neuroblastoma in the stage 4s. Observation and supportive care is favourable ^[6, 15, 18].

RECURRENT NEUROBLASTOMA:-

Recurrent neuroblastoma is found in the area where the first tumor was formed and the treatment can be done by

- Surgery followed by observation.
- Chemotherapy followed by surgery¹⁴.

Treatment for recurrent tumors that were spread to other parts include

- Chemotherapy followed by surgery and observation.

Treatment For recurrent High-Risk Neuroblastoma-

Treatment for recurrent neuroblastoma includes:

- ★Combination chemotherapy
- ★Iodine 131-MIBG to relieve symptoms and improve quality of life.
- ★A second dose of high risk chemotherapy
- ★Tyrosine kinase inhibitor therapy for patients who have altered ALK gene ^[6, 15, 18].

Patients with Recurrent CNS Neuroblastoma-

Treatment for neuroblastoma that recurs (comes back) in the central nervous system (CNS; brain and spinal cord) may include the following:

- Surgery to remove the tumor in the CNS followed by radiation therapy.
- A clinical trial of a new therapy ^[6, 19].

TREATMENTS BEING STUDIED FOR PROGRESSIVE/RECURRENT NEUROBLASTOMA:-

Some of the treatments being studied in clinical trials for neuroblastoma that recurs (comes back) or progresses (grows, spreads, or does not respond to treatment) include the following:

- Checking a sample of the patient's tumor for certain gene changes. The type of targeted therapy that will be given to the patient depends on the type of gene change.
- Lenalidomide and monoclonal antibody therapy (Dinutuximab)¹¹ with or without isotretinoin²⁰.
- Iodine 131-MIBG therapy given alone or with other anticancer drugs¹⁴.
- Immunotherapy (vaccine therapy).
- Tyrosine kinase inhibitor (crizotinib) and combination chemotherapy^[6, 19].

ADVANCE TREATMENT:-

- ❖ Cytotoxic agents. Eg: - Vincristine sulfate, Topotecan, Irinotecan, Temozolomide, Cisplatin and Etoposide
- ❖ Retinoids. Eg: - Isotretinoin have reduced the risk of recurrence after treatment in children with High-risk neuroblastoma²⁰. Newer, potentially more effective Retinoids, such as Fenretinide¹⁶.
- ❖ Immunotherapy - monoclonal antibodies (usually anti-GD2), Radioimmunoconjugate therapy²².
- ❖ Radioiodinated MIBG - 131I-metaiodobenzylguanidine (MIBG)^[14, 21].
- ❖ Antiangiogenic therapy
- ❖ Late effects of therapy⁷

SIDE EFFECTS OF TREATMENT-

Problems that occurs when treatment affects healthy tissues or organs.

- Anemia, loss of Appetite, Constipation, Diarrhea, Edema, Fatigue, Fertility issues in boys & girls; & men, women, Hair loss, Thrombocytopenia, Infection & neutropenia, Memory or concentration problems, nausea & vomiting, nerve problems, pain, sleep problems, urinary & bladder problems, sexual health issues in men & women⁹.

CONCLUSION

Neuroblastoma is a serious condition seen in children. Appropriate therapy should be properly studied and clinical trials should be continued for the betterment of treatment methods. A multidisciplinary health care team should always be involved and provide the therapeutic and supportive care effectively.

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CONFLICTS OF INTEREST:

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest regarding this article.

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